

Speculation on the Correspondence Principle and X and T Independence

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Traditionally a high energy solution of the time-independent Schrodinger equation is compared with a classical result. In particular, the quantum spatial density $W(x)W(x)$ where $W(x)$ is the bound wavefunction has humps and zero regions, but an envelope through the peaks is roughly equal to $C/v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is the classical velocity. $W(x)W(x)$ is the spatial density and $C/v(x)$ is proportional to dt , the time a particle spends in a fixed dx length.

In this note we make use of (1) namely that the free particle classical action A (relativistic or nonrelativistic) may be written with $v=x/t$ and x and t varied independently yielding $A = -Et + px$. A is a Lorentz invariant, but with x and t independent this implies Et and px are constant. This suggests a characteristic length proportional to $1/p$ and a characteristic time proportional to $1/E$ as suggested in a previous note. A probability distribution is required to establish $1/p$ units in space such that it goes to 0 at the start and endpoints of $1/p$. This implies a periodic probability function, but the particle has equal probability to be at any x so a two dimensional form with two periodic functions such that the modulus is 1 is needed.

We argue that the basic humps and troughs in a quantum bound state are due to Lorentz invariance and x and t independence. Classical mechanics on the other hand is based on $x(t)$. Thus the two are incompatible. The constraint: $KE \text{ average} + V(x) = E_n$ is enough to allow for relative peak heights to be in the ratio $v(x_2) / v(x_1)$, but the spatial density humps and the independence of x and t are uniquely quantum mechanical. This begs the question: Are these humps physical? It seems that experiments suggest that large objects (e.g. 70 kg) (2) may have quantum motion suggesting that $x(t)$ may be an approximation.

X and T Independence in the Classical Action

The action A is well known from classical physics. If one considers the free particle action (relativistic $-m_0 t \sqrt{1-vv}$ ($c=1$)) or (nonrelativistic $t \cdot \frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2$), writes $v=x/t$ and varies x and t independently then:

$$dA/dx \text{ partial} = p \text{ and } dA/dt \text{ partial} = -E \quad ((1))$$

Classical mechanics, however, is based on the idea that $x(t)$, which is the opposite idea of x and t being independent. ((1)) leads to:

$$A = -Et + px \quad ((2))$$

((2)) is Lorentz invariant, but if t and x are independent, the $-Et$ and px should be constant i.e. there are characteristic times and lengths in the system :

$$T \text{ characteristic is proportional to } 1/E \quad \text{and} \quad L \text{ characteristic is proportional to } 1/p \quad ((3))$$

In particular, if there is a characteristic length L an object with p should manifest this length. This suggests a periodic probability distribution in 1D of $F(px)$ where F is a periodic function which is 0 at the start and endpoints of C/p where C is a constant. This leads to a problem because probability cannot disappear at the endpoints. As a remedy, one may consider a two dimensional dynamic probability such as:

$\cos(px) + i \sin(px)$ which is different for p and $-p$, but has a modulus of 1 for both ((4))

The modulus of 1 allows for the existence of a characteristic length together with an equal probability for the particle to be at any x . Note both $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ may take on negative values. This is key for interference. Mathematically the negative values are needed to make $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ continuous with a continuous derivative. Physically there is wave behaviour occurring, albeit probability wave behaviour.

Given that $\exp(ipx)$ is a probability it should add. This allows for interference as the unit modulus property is usually broken by a sum. In other words there will be points with more probability than others as in a two slit interference pattern or bound state (e.g. oscillator). The possible negative values of $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ allow for the creation of "new" characteristic lengths through interference. For the bound state these are built by different $\exp(ipx)$ terms having different characteristic lengths. For two slit interference, $\exp(i p x_1)$ and $\exp(i p x_2)$ may be out of phase and yield points with no probability. Ultimately we argue, however, that this occurs because of x - t independence and Lorentz invariance i.e. the existence of a characteristic length and the idea of periodic cycling between these length units. Given that the particle must somehow manifest this periodic length in space, it seems that the only way to do this is to have zero spatial density (at least in 1D) at start and endpoints (as argued in previous notes).

Bound State

If one wishes to consider a bound state with a potential $V(x)$ then one may obtain the time-independent Schrodinger equation using $\exp(ipx)$'s which manifest the idea of x - t independence (no t is used) and incorporate the characteristic length proportional to $1/p$ i.e. use $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$. Imposing conservation of average energy at each x yields:

$$\{ \text{Sum over } p \frac{a(p) p^2}{2m} \exp(ipx) \} / \{ \text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx) \} + V(x) = E_n \quad ((5))$$

((5)) is the Schrodinger time-independent equation, but we argue this is based on x - t independence and a $1/p$ proportional length due to Lorentz invariance.

Thus such a solution should always be incompatible with the classical result $x(t)$ because the system creates its own humps and troughs in $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx)$.

Physical Evidence for Classical Objects with Quantum Behaviour

A question arises as to whether the hump density result of using $\exp(ipx)$'s i.e. assuming x - t independence and Lorentz invariance for px leading to a characteristic length have physical relevance. They do for two slit interference, but what about large objects? Apparently objects on

the scale of a human may exhibit quantum “jiggles”. We suggest this may be a manifestation of x - t independence and Lorentz invariance and that $x(t)$ is an approximation which treats space and time as mathematical points in terms of motion and energy.

Conclusion

In conclusion we suggest that quantum mechanics and classical mechanics are fundamentally different in that the latter assumes $x(t)$ while the former treats x and t as independent for a free particle. In such a case the free particle action (relativistic or nonrelativistic) is $-Et+px$, a Lorentz invariant. Given the independence of x and t , px and Et should separately be constant suggesting a characteristic time proportional to $1/E$ and a length proportional to $1/p$. This suggests a breaking of space into $1/p$ length units marked by a distribution which should have 0 values at the start and endpoints. Probability cannot vanish so one needs to introduce two dimensions. (These ideas have been discussed in previous notes.) In this note we argue that these results lead to $\exp(ipx)$ for a free particle and humps for a bound state which remain in the high energy limit. We suggest that the “quantum fluctuation” aspect may be physically relevant i.e. x and t may be independent to an extent and Lorentz invariance of px and $-Et$ separately may play an important role in that large objects (or the order of 70 kg) may show “quantum jiggles” (2). Furthermore $x(t)$ may only be an approximation.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Lagrangian/Action Formalism as a Flow Scheme? (preprint, zenodo, 2021)
2. <https://news.mit.edu/2020/quantum-fluctuations-jiggle-objects-0701>